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Activation of TNF by cGAMP.

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We demonstrate here activation of tumor necrosis alpha encoded by *Tnf* in human cells stimulated with the cyclic dinucleotide second messenger cGAMP (cyclic GMP-AMP).

Citations

1. Swanson, K.V., Junkins, R.D., Kurkjian, C.J., Holley-Guthrie, E., Pendse, A.A., El Morabiti, R., Petrucelli, A., Barber, G.N., Benedict, C.A. and Ting, J.P.Y., 2017. A noncanonical function of cGAMP in inflammasome priming and activation. *Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 214(12), pp.3611-3626.

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